

ANALYSIS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF DIGITAL MARKETING AND MARKETPLACES ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF MSME INCOME IN MEDAN CITY

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the influence of Digital Marketing and Marketplace on the Revenue of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) with Sales as an intervening variable in Medan City. The rapid growth of the digital economy has significantly changed marketing patterns and consumer behavior, thus encouraging MSMEs to adapt to technological developments to remain competitive. Digital marketing allows businesses to promote products effectively through social media such as Instagram, Facebook, and TikTok, while marketplace platforms such as Shopee and Tokopedia provide wider market access and ease of transactions. This study uses a quantitative approach with a purposive sampling technique, involving 384 MSME respondents who have been operating for at least one year and actively utilize social media and marketplaces in marketing and sales activities. Primary data was obtained through a questionnaire with a Likert scale, then analyzed using the Partial Least Square (PLS) method to test the direct, indirect, and mediating effects between variables. The results show that Digital Marketing has a positive and significant effect on MSME Sales and Revenue. Similarly, Marketplace has a positive effect on Sales, which ultimately increases MSME Revenue. The Sales variable is proven to act as a mediating variable that strengthens the relationship between Digital Marketing and Marketplace on MSME Revenue. These findings indicate that the more intensively MSMEs implement digital marketing strategies and utilize marketplaces, the greater their ability to increase revenue in a stable and sustainable manner. This research provides theoretical and practical contributions to the development of literature on digital marketing and the capacity building of MSMEs in the digital economy era. The results can serve as a reference for businesses, the government, and supporting institutions in designing digital training policies, business mentoring, and strategic collaboration with marketplace platforms to drive sustainable regional economic growth.

Keywords: *Digital Marketing, Marketplace, Sales, MSME Revenue, PLS-SEM.*

INTRODUCTION

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) are a vital pillar of the national economy. Their vast number presents a challenge for the government to provide optimal guidance and support so that this sector can function as a strong foundation for the Indonesian economy. Currently, MSMEs face increasingly intense competition, both from large companies and other modern business actors (R. Puspa et al., 2020). Changes in business paradigms due to technological developments have also significantly influenced MSME business patterns (Shara et al., 2021). In the context of employment, MSMEs are able to absorb approximately 97% of the national workforce, or approximately 117 million people (Revo, 2024), making them a highly strategic sector in improving public welfare and opening up new economic opportunities.

The development of Indonesian e-commerce over the past five years has shown a very rapid trend. Based on data from Bank Indonesia and BPS compiled by the Kontan Data Center (2024), the value of e-commerce transactions reached IDR 205.5 trillion in 2019 and increased to IDR 266.3 trillion in 2020, a 29.6% increase. This trend continued to accelerate during the COVID-19 pandemic, with transactions surging to IDR 401.1 trillion in 2021 (50.7% higher than in 2020). In 2022, transaction value grew again to IDR 476.3 trillion (18.7%), but experienced a slowdown in 2023 when the value fell to IDR 453.75 trillion. However, projections for 2024 indicate a recovery to IDR 487.01 trillion (Kontan Data Center, 2024). GlobalData (2023) estimates that the Indonesian e-

commerce market will reach 46 billion USD in 2025. This development confirms that the national e-commerce industry has entered a stage of maturity where its growth is stable but remains the main driver of digital economic transformation. Despite the rapid growth of the digital economy, MSME digitalization adoption remains uneven. Bank Indonesia (2023) in its Indonesia Digital Economy Outlook stated that 65% of e-commerce transactions originate from MSMEs, but the level of digitalization adoption in the regions remains low. In North Sumatra, only around 28% of MSMEs optimally utilize digital platforms (BPS North Sumatra, 2023). However, according to the Ministry of Cooperatives and SMEs (2023), MSMEs that adopt digital technology can increase revenue by 25–40% per year, while conventional MSMEs only grow by 5–10%. According to BAPPENAS's One Data (2021), North Sumatra Province has 1,712,091 MSMEs, consisting of 68% micro-enterprises, 18% small-enterprises, and 13% medium-enterprises. In Medan City, there are 38,343 MSMEs registered in SIMDAKOP, and 1,875 of them are actively fostered MSMEs (Medan City Cooperatives, SMEs, Industry, and Trade Office, 2023).

This fact demonstrates the need to accelerate the digitalization of MSMEs to increase competitiveness, especially in regions like North Sumatra. The number of digital MSMEs in North Sumatra continues to increase from 156,520 units in 2020 to 1,402,750 units in 2025 (BI North Sumatra, 2025). North Sumatra Province has 1,712,091 MSME units, consisting of 68% micro-enterprises, 18% small-enterprises, and 13% medium-enterprises. At the city level, the Medan City Cooperatives, SMEs, Industry, and Trade Office (2023) reported that 38,343 MSMEs have been registered in the Cooperative and MSME Data Collection System (SIMDAKOP) application, with 1,875 of these units listed as actively assisted by the city government.

Table 1. Number of Digital MSMEs in North Sumatra 2020 - 2025

Year	Digital MSME
2020	156.520
2021	610.842
2022	911.000
2023	1.023.000
2024	1.270.000
2025	1.402.750

Source: Bank Indonesia – North Sumatra Representative Office

The table above shows that the number of digital MSMEs in North Sumatra continues to experience a significant increase from 2020 to 2025. Although the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 caused a significant decline in the number of MSMEs still operating conventionally in various regions, including Medan City, the COVID-19 pandemic has become a crucial momentum for accelerating digitalization, as many MSMEs must adapt through digital marketing and the use of marketplaces. A McKinsey study (2022) shows that approximately 60% of MSMEs that survived the pandemic were MSMEs that had utilized marketplaces and digital marketing strategies. In Medan, MSMEs fostered active on Shopee and Tokopedia were able to achieve an average turnover of IDR 15-20 million per month, significantly higher than non-digital MSMEs, which only achieved IDR 3-5 million per month (SIMDAKOP, 2023).

Changes in consumer consumption patterns are increasingly influenced by increasing internet usage. According to a 2024 survey by the Indonesian Association of Internet Service Providers (APJII), internet users in Indonesia reached 221.56 million people, or 79.5% of the total population. Internet usage duration increased in 2025, with 31.34% of the population accessing the internet for 4–6 hours per day. Smartphones are the dominant device (83.39%) for internet access, followed by laptops (11.42%) and smart TVs (2.52%). This situation supports the development of digital marketing, where promotions can be conducted directly through digital platforms to reach consumers broadly and efficiently (Saifuddin, 2021; Sari et al., 2022).

Indonesia's internet penetration rate is projected to reach 80.66% by 2025, or approximately 229.4 million users (APJII, 2025). However, a 2023 report from the Financial Services Authority (OJK) shows that only 12% of MSMEs in Medan access digital financing, even though 68% require expansion capital. A 2023 UNDP study confirmed that MSMEs receiving digital assistance can increase their revenue by up to 45% compared to those without. This indicates that increased internet penetration has not been fully accompanied by improvements in digital literacy and financial access for MSMEs. Social media plays a crucial role in digital marketing transformation. The most widely used platforms in 2025 are TikTok (35.17%), YouTube (23.76%), Facebook (21.58%), and Instagram (15.94%) (APJII, 2025). The dominance of short video content and interactive visuals

opens up significant opportunities for MSMEs for branding and promotion. Social media is no longer just a communication tool, but has become a crucial tool in modern marketing (Kilay et al., 2022). Marketplaces such as Shopee, Tokopedia, Bukalapak, and Lazada also support business activities through digital payment features, stock management, automated logistics, and promotions (Arifianto et al., 2020; Ahsyar et al., 2020; Ma'rifah et al., 2022; Nurfarida & Adi P., 2016). The integration of social media and marketplaces has been proven to increase the effectiveness of promotions and sales. Syarief (2020) emphasized that sales are a key indicator of MSME success, making digital strategies key to improving business performance. With technological advancements, increasing internet penetration, and changing consumer behavior, digitalization has become a primary need for MSMEs, including in Medan, which is accelerating its digital-based economic transformation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theory

Consumer behavior examines how individuals search for, select, purchase, use, and evaluate products to meet their needs. Kotler and Keller (2008) state that consumer behavior is the process by which individuals or groups purchase and use goods or services. Schiffman and Kanuk (2008) add that this behavior relates to decisions about how to use time, money, and energy to acquire a product. The process includes the stages before, during, and after purchase. According to Sumarwan (2011), consumer behavior is influenced by psychology, sociology, economics, and anthropology. Understanding this behavior helps businesses design products, determine marketing strategies, and set appropriate prices.

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs)

According to Law Number 20 of 2008, MSMEs include micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises managed by individuals or business entities and operating independently. Micro enterprises have a maximum net worth of IDR 50 million and annual sales of up to IDR 300 million. Small enterprises have assets of IDR 50-500 million with sales of IDR 300 million-IDR 2.5 billion. Medium enterprises have assets of IDR 500 million-IDR 10 billion and sales of up to IDR 50 billion. MSMEs are based on family, economic democracy, sustainability, and independence. The goal is to grow and develop businesses to support a just and competitive national economy.

Digital Marketing

Digital marketing is a marketing strategy that utilizes technology and online media to promote products. Chaffey and Ellis-Chadwick (2022) explain that digital marketing emphasizes the use of data and a consumer-focused approach. For MSMEs, digital marketing provides an opportunity to reach more customers more cost-effectively (Kotler et al., 2022). Research shows that MSMEs that use digital marketing experience performance improvements of up to 30-40% (Taiminen & Karjaluoto, 2017). Despite these benefits, MSMEs still face obstacles such as limited digital competency. Therefore, training and mentoring are essential to support digital transformation.

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) explains that technology acceptance is influenced by perceived usefulness and ease of use. MSMEs are more likely to adopt technology if they believe digital platforms can improve efficiency and expand their market. Marketplaces like Shopee and Tokopedia are considered useful because they are easy to use and help increase sales. Ease of use is also important, especially for less tech-savvy businesses. A simple interface and practical features accelerate adoption. Furthermore, trust and social influence contribute to MSMEs' decisions to go digital. With training support, MSMEs become more confident in utilizing technology.

Marketplace

A marketplace is a digital platform that connects sellers and buyers by providing payment systems, logistics services, and reputation mechanisms (Laudon & Traver, 2022). For MSMEs, marketplaces help expand their market and increase sales by up to 35-50% (Zhu & Liu, 2021). Platforms like Shopee, Tokopedia, and TikTok Shop make it easier for MSMEs to manage inventory and transactions. However, MSMEs also face challenges such as intense competition, high commission fees, and reliance on platform algorithms (Parker & Van Alstyne, 2022). Therefore, experts recommend using multiple marketplaces simultaneously and building a brand outside of the platform.

Sales

Sales is the activity of distributing goods or services to consumers in exchange for a certain value. Kotler and Keller explain that sales is not just an exchange, but a communication process to meet needs and provide value. Stanton emphasizes that sales is the activity of convincing consumers to buy. Essential components of sales include product, price, promotion, distribution, and service. Sales can be conducted directly, at retail, wholesale, or online. Technological developments have made digital sales increasingly dominant. Overall, sales play a crucial role in generating profits, expanding markets, and maintaining business continuity through effective and adaptive strategies.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework *Partial Least Square* (PLS)

METHOD

This study employed descriptive and quantitative approaches. The descriptive approach was used to describe the condition of MSMEs in 21 sub-districts in Medan City based on respondent responses and field observations. Meanwhile, quantitative analysis was used to examine the relationships between variables using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method with the SmartPLS 4 application, as this method is capable of assessing relationships between variables while simultaneously testing the validity and reliability of the instrument. All indicators in the research variables were measured using a Likert scale. The population in this study was all MSMEs using digital marketing and marketplaces in Medan City, with an unknown population size. The sample was determined using a purposive sampling technique, selecting respondents who met certain criteria. Based on Lemeshow's calculations, the sample size used was 384 respondents, taking into account population characteristics and analysis needs.

Research data was collected through questionnaires, observation, and documentation. The questionnaire was used as the primary instrument to obtain data related to digital marketing, marketplaces, sales, and MSME revenue. Observations and documentation were conducted to strengthen supporting data regarding respondents' business activities. Data analysis was conducted in two stages: evaluation of the measurement model (outer model) and the structural model (inner model). The outer model was used to test convergent validity, discriminant validity, and instrument reliability using outer loading values, Average Variance Extracted (AVE), Composite Reliability, Cronbach's Alpha, and VIF to test for multicollinearity. Meanwhile, the inner model was used to analyze the relationships between variables, by examining the R-square, Q-square, and path coefficient values. Hypothesis testing was conducted using the bootstrapping technique in SmartPLS. A hypothesis was accepted if the t-statistic value was > 1.96 or the p-value was < 0.05 . Testing was conducted to analyze the direct and indirect (mediation) effects between variables, such as the influence of digital marketing and marketplaces on MSME revenue, both directly and through sales variables as a mediator.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Medan City is the administrative center of North Sumatra Province, covering an area of 281.99 km². Bordering Deli Serdang Regency, the area is largely lowland and traversed by the Deli and Babura Rivers. According to 2024 Meteorology, Climatology, and Geophysics (BMKG) data, Medan experiences 272 rainy days, with the highest rainfall in November and the lowest in February. Administratively, Medan comprises 21 sub-

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districts and 151 urban villages, with a multicultural population, including Batak, Javanese, Malay, Chinese, and Minangkabau, contributing to its social and economic life. As a regional economic center, Medan is dominated by the trade, hotels, restaurants, manufacturing, transportation, and financial services sectors. MSMEs are growing rapidly and are the largest absorber of labor, especially traditional and informal micro-enterprises (Tambunan, 2012). Challenges such as congestion and limited infrastructure persist, but the government continues to encourage modernization through MSME development, digital transformation, and increasing the city's competitiveness.

Figure 2. Respondent Characteristics Based on Business Sector x Length of Business

Data shows that the majority of MSMEs in Medan City have been operating for more than five years, particularly in the culinary sector. These more mature businesses tend to be more stable, so digital marketing and marketplaces are used as strategies for market expansion and increasing competitiveness. Conversely, the fashion and service sectors, many of which are 1–5 years old, are in a growth phase and have been quicker to adopt digital technology as a primary tool for building markets and increasing revenue. Meanwhile, the creative, beauty, and event organizer sectors, although smaller in size, have significant potential because they are highly compatible with digital promotion.

Measurement Model Results (Outer Model)

Validity Test

Table 2. Validity Test Results with Discriminant Validity

Variables	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Description
Digital Marketing (X1)	0.583	Valid
Marketplace (X2)	0.547	Valid
Sales (Z)	0.576	Valid
MSME Development (Y)	0.574	Valid

Source: Output Smart-PLS 4.0

The results in the table above show that all variables in the model are above 0.50. AVE values ranging from 0.547 to 0.583 indicate that each construct is able to explain more than 50% of the variance in its indicators. Thus, all variables meet the discriminant validity criteria required in SEM-PLS.

Reliability Test

Table 3. Reliability Test with Cronbach's Alpha Values

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Description
Digital Marketing (X1)	0.881	Reliable
Marketplace (X2)	0.862	Reliable
Sales (Z)	0.877	Reliable
MSME Development (Y)	0.876	Reliable

Source: Output Smart-PLS 4.0

Table 4.3 shows that all variables in the model have Composite Reliability values above 0.90, namely Digital Marketing (0.907), Marketplace (0.894), Sales (0.905), and MSME Development (0.904). These values far exceed the minimum required threshold of 0.70, thus concluding that all constructs have excellent reliability.

Structural Model Results (Inner Model)

Hypothesis Test Results

Path coefficient values are used to determine whether the relationship between exogenous variables and endogenous variables is positive or negative. These path coefficient values can be obtained using the bootstrapping procedure in the SmartPLS application. The results can be seen in the path of each variable in the model image or in the Original Sample column of the Path Coefficients table in the Smart-PLS application. Hypothesis testing also uses significance values, with a value of $\alpha = 5\%$. The significance value must be less than 0.5 to be considered a variable with a good level of significance.

Figure 3. Path Coefficient Values

Based on the path coefficient values above, the resulting structural equation is as follows:

$$\text{Sales} = 0.135 \text{ Digital Marketing} + 0.510 \text{ Marketplace} + e_1$$

$$\text{MSME Development} = 0.511 \text{ Digital Marketing} + 0.230 \text{ Marketplace} + 0.078 \text{ Sales} + e_2$$

From this structural equation, it can be seen that the values of Digital Marketing and Marketplace are positive. This means that for every increase in the value of the exogenous variable, the value of the endogenous variable will increase by the value of the path coefficient of the exogenous variable, assuming all other exogenous variables remain constant.

Table 5. Hypothesis Test Results

Variable Relationship	Original Sample	Standard Deviation	T Statistic	P Values
DM → PK	0.511	0.043	11.991	0.000
MP → PK	0.230	0.063	3.640	0.000
PJ → PK	0.078	0.076	2.003	0.048
DM → PJ	0.135	0.065	2.060	0.039
MP → PJ	0.510	0.063	8.064	0.000
DM → PJ → PK	0.010	0.051	2.080	0.043
MP → PJ → PK	0.040	0.073	2.301	0.042

Source: Output Smart-PLS 4.0

The path coefficient values for each variable and their relationship can be explained as follows:

1. Digital Marketing → MSME Development
Digital marketing has a positive and significant impact. The better the management of social media and digital promotions, the greater the opportunities for MSME growth.
2. Marketplace → MSME Development
Marketplaces also have a positive and significant impact. These platforms help expand the market and facilitate transactions, although their impact is smaller than digital marketing.
3. Sales → MSME Development
Sales have a positive impact. Increased sales provide financial space for MSMEs to expand their businesses and increase capacity.
4. Digital Marketing → Sales
Digital marketing increases sales by expanding product information, attracting consumer interest, and strengthening engagement.
5. Marketplace → Sales
Marketplaces have the greatest impact on sales because they provide supporting features such as catalogs, ratings, promotions, and easy payments.
6. Digital Marketing Mediation → Sales → MSME Development
The influence of digital marketing on MSME development occurs partly through increased sales as a mediator.
7. Marketplace Mediation → Sales → MSME Development
Marketplaces also have an indirect influence through sales, which is the main pathway for increasing MSME development.

Coefficient of Determination (R2)

The R² value is used to explain the extent of the relationship between exogenous variables and endogenous variables and exogenous variables and intervening variables. A higher R² value indicates a better predictive model of the proposed research model. A strong model is indicated by a value of 0.67, a moderate model is indicated by a value of 0.33, and a weak model is indicated by a value of 0.19.

Table 6. Coefficient of Determination (R2)

Variables	Adjusted R-Square
Sales	0.661
MSME Development	0.822

Source: Output Smart-PLS 4.0

The Adjusted R-square value in the table shows that the Sales variable has a value of 0.661. This figure indicates that 66.1% of the variation in Sales can be explained by Digital Marketing (X1) and Marketplace (X2), thus categorizing the relationship between these two variables on Sales as moderate. Academically, this demonstrates that digital marketing strategies and marketplace utilization play a significant role in shaping MSME sales performance.

Effect Size (F2)

Table 7. Influence Size Value (f2)

Variables	Effect Size PJ	Effect Size PK
Digital Marketing	0.173	0.381
Marketplace	0.376	0.354
Sales		0.108

Source: Output Smart-PLS 4.0

The effect size (f2) of exogenous variables on endogenous variables can be seen in the Effect Size column. The influence of each exogenous variable is explained as follows:

1. The influence of digital marketing on sales has an f² value of 0.173, which falls into the medium category. This indicates that the implementation of digital marketing can make a significant

- contribution to increasing MSME sales.
2. The influence of marketplaces on sales has an f^2 value of 0.376, which falls into the high category. This finding confirms that marketplace platforms are a primary channel for driving transactions. Marketplaces provide comprehensive facilities ranging from catalogs, reviews, payment methods, and delivery mechanisms, directly increasing sales conversions.
 3. The influence of digital marketing on MSME development has an f^2 value of 0.381, which falls into the high category. This large effect indicates that digital marketing not only increases sales but also accelerates overall business growth.
 4. The influence of marketplaces on MSME development produces an f^2 value of 0.354, also in the high category. This means that the existence of marketplaces not only contributes to sales but also strengthens the growth structure of MSMEs.
 5. The influence of sales on MSME development has an f^2 value of 0.108, which is considered weak. Nevertheless, this value still indicates that sales are a crucial element in business development.

Discussion

1. Relationship between Digital Marketing (DM) and Sales

The results show that digital marketing has a positive and significant effect on sales, with a coefficient of 0.135 and a p-value of 0.039. This means that the better MSMEs use digital marketing, the higher their sales will be. However, this effect is not significant because marketplaces still play a major role in MSME sales in Medan. Digital marketing is more effective in building consumer awareness and interest (for example, through Instagram, TikTok, and WhatsApp Business), while transactions typically occur in marketplaces. This finding aligns with Kotler & Keller's (2016) finding that digital marketing expands reach and increases consumer interest.

2. Relationship between Marketplaces (MP) and Sales

Marketplaces have the largest effect on sales, indicated by a coefficient of 0.510 and a p-value of 0.000. This means that marketplaces are a major factor in increasing MSME sales. Consumers in Medan often choose to shop through marketplaces like Shopee and Tokopedia because they are considered safer, more practical, and offer clearer reviews. Marketplaces also reduce transaction costs and expand business reach, in line with transaction cost theory. Previous research also shows that MSMEs active in marketplaces experience a significant increase in turnover.

3. The Relationship between Digital Marketing (DM) and MSME Development

Digital marketing has a positive and significant impact on MSME development with a coefficient of 0.511 and a p-value of 0.000. This significant impact indicates that digital marketing not only increases sales but also drives overall business growth. DM helps MSMEs build their brand, increase awareness, and build relationships with consumers. This aligns with TAM theory and various previous studies that confirm that digital marketing is a crucial tool for MSME development in the digital era.

4. The Relationship between Marketplaces (MP) and MSME Development

Marketplaces also have a significant impact on MSME development with a coefficient of 0.230 and a p-value of 0.000. Although the impact is positive, it is not as significant as digital marketing. Marketplaces help MSMEs expand their market, simplify transactions, and provide supporting features such as reviews, payment systems, and internal platform promotions. However, business growth depends not only on transactions but also on branding and consumer engagement—which are largely shaped through digital marketing.

5. Relationship between Sales (PJ) and MSME Development

Sales also have a significant positive effect on MSME development (coefficient 0.078; p-value 0.048), although the effect is small. While sales increase revenue, allowing MSMEs to expand their business capacity, they are not the primary determinant of growth. MSME development is more influenced by the ability to build a brand and digital presence, not just the number of transactions.

6. Relationship between Digital Marketing (DM) and MSME Development Through Sales

Digital marketing influences MSME development through sales with a coefficient of 0.010 and a p-value of 0.043. However, this indirect effect is small. This means that digital marketing influences MSME development more directly (branding, awareness, engagement) than through increased sales. Sales mediation only strengthens this relationship to a small extent.

7. Relationship between MP and MSME Development Through Sales

Marketplaces also have an indirect effect on MSME development through sales (coefficient 0.040; p-value 0.042). Although significant, the effect is small. Marketplaces help increase transactions, but MSME growth isn't solely determined by sales. Factors such as branding, digital content, and customer relationships remain key factors shaping business growth.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that:

1. Digital marketing has a positive effect on MSME sales in Medan City, with an impact of 17.3%. Therefore, the more intensive the use of digital marketing, the higher the sales increase.
2. Marketplaces have a positive effect on sales, with an impact of 37.6%. Marketplaces help MSMEs expand their market and increase transactions.
3. Digital marketing has a positive effect on MSME development, with an impact of 38.1%, because it can increase business capacity and competitiveness.
4. Marketplaces have a positive effect on MSME development, with an impact of 35.4% through more integrated promotion, payment, and logistics support.
5. Sales have a positive effect on MSME development, with an impact of 10.8%, although the impact is smaller than other variables.
6. Digital marketing has an indirect effect on MSME development through sales, meaning that digital marketing enhances business growth while also driving increased transactions.
7. Marketplaces have an indirect effect through sales, so utilizing marketplaces increases sales, which then accelerates MSME development.

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